

Information Literacy Skills and Utilization of Online Resources by Undergraduates in University Libraries in South-South, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the contribution of information literacy skills to the utilization of online library resources by undergraduates in university libraries in south-south Nigeria. The survey research design was adopted for the study. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to guide the study. A total of six hundred and five (605) students' which is 5% of the sampled population of 12,100 registered undergraduate library users of the 2023/2024 academic session was used for the study. The questionnaire titled Information Literacy Skills and Utilization of Online Resources Questionnaire (ILSUORQ) was the instrument for data collection. The reliability estimate of the instrument was established through Cronbach Alpha reliability method. The reliability coefficient ranges from 0.75 to 0.83 which was high enough. To achieve the purpose of the study 3 null hypotheses were formulated to guide it. Regression analysis was the statistical technique employed to test the hypotheses under study. Each hypothesis was tested at .05 level of significance. The result of the analysis revealed that, ability to identify information, capacity to find information, skills to evaluate information, significantly predict utilization of online Library resources by undergraduates. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that, University libraries should implement training programs and workshops that focus on improving students' ability to identify relevant information, and prioritize teaching students how to find information within online databases and digital platforms, and training to help students critically evaluate the information they access online.

Keywords: Information, Literacy, Students, Online Resources, Utilization, South-South Nigeria.

Introduction

The Nigerian educational system aims at the training and development of the individual's mind in the understanding of their immediate environment and the world around them. The acquisition of appropriate skills and competencies as equipment for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the society are key factors the Nigerian Educational system. Libraries help to promote the acquisition of knowledge and skills, as well as the development of critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. The

library in supporting the teaching, learning, and research activities of the university educational system has developed over time different knowledge acquisition skills for the library user to be self-reliant and independent learners. In

providing an enabling environment for the learner, the library acquires online resources to support the academic activities of the undergraduate library user. (Ibukun & Aboluwodi 2010)

Information literacy is important for today's learners, it promotes problem-solving approaches and thinking skills asking questions and seeking answers, finding information, forming opinions, evaluating sources, and making decisions fostering successful learners, effective contributors, confident individuals, and responsible citizens. The importance of Information Literacy to students' success cannot be overemphasized as noted by Toyo (2017), information literacy allows students to develop the capacity for independent and critical learning that is the hallmark of university education which equips the learner with the capability to update their knowledge and skills during and after graduation.

According to Ani and Ahiauzu, (2018), an information literate student should be able to identify the need for information, determine the extent of information needed, access information efficiently, critically evaluate information and its sources, classify, store, manipulate, and redraft information collected or generated, incorporate selected information into their knowledge base, use information effectively to learn, create new knowledge, solve problems and make decisions, understand economic, legal, social, political and cultural issues in the use of information, access and use information ethically and legally use information and knowledge for participative citizenship and social responsibility and experience information literacy as part of independent learning and lifelong learning. (Toyo, 2017, Freeman 2010).

This study is focused on determining the extent to which information literacy skills are related to the utilization of online resources by undergraduates in university libraries in the South-South Zone of Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to investigate whether information literacy skills predicts the utilization of online library resources by undergraduates sampled for the study in university libraries in south-south Nigeria.

Statement of hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses.

1. The ability to identify information does not significantly predict the utilization of online resources
2. Capacity to find information does not significantly predict the utilization of online resources
3. Skills to evaluate information do not significantly predict the utilization of online resources by undergraduates in university libraries in Nigeria

Review of related literature

Information literacy is an essential aspect of education for the proper functioning of the learner to be able to compete favorably in a changing global society. Information literacy is the ability to Identify, locate, evaluate, cite, communicate, and effectively use information from various sources. It involves understanding how information is organized, how to assess its credibility, and how to use it ethically and responsibly. It is a critical skill set in today's digital age, where information is easily accessible but not always reliable.

Ikenwe and Anaehobi (2020), in their study, investigated the relationship between lecturers' ability to identify the extent of information need, access information, and utilization of digital library resources in Federal Universities, in Southern Nigeria. A correlational research design was adopted. The population of the study comprised 6,653 lecturers with a sample size of 665 selected through a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Instruments for data collection were cognitive tests and questionnaires used for utilization of digital library resources. Kuder–Richardson method was used to establish the internal reliability coefficient, yielding the scores 0.77, and 0.78, respectively, and Cronbach alpha for questionnaire yielding 0.81. Data collected were analyzed using the Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient. In testing the hypotheses, the p-value was used to determine the level of significance at the 0.05 alpha level. The results show a low positive relationship between abilities to identify the extent of information, and access information in the utilization of digital library resources. The hypotheses were rejected, indicating a positive relationship between ability to identify the extent of information need and utilization of digital library resources.

Ugwulebo and Okuonghae (2021) investigated information literacy skills and utilization of electronic information resources by postgraduate students in Nigeria. The study adopted the ex post facto research design to investigate the relationship that exists between information

literacy skill variables and the utilization of electronic information resources by postgraduate students in Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 3,744 postgraduate students from three federal universities in Nigeria, namely; University of Uyo, Uyo; University of Calabar, Calabar and University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Port Harcourt. The sample size for the study is 374 respondents which was determined using Taro Yamane's (1969) method for sampling. Data was collected through the instrument of a questionnaire and the data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The findings from the study revealed that a significant relationship exists among postgraduate students' knowledge of electronic resources, search skills, access to information, information evaluation capability, and their utilization of electronic information resources. The study concluded that information literacy programs must be included in the curriculum of students across all levels as this will help improve their overall academic achievement.

Michelle, Kira, Heather., Carolyn, Daniel, Donald, Cynthia, and Whitney (2014) in their study, examined how educational intervention in a doctor of pharmacy (PharmD) degree program increases pharmacy students' ability to identify plagiarism. Methods employed were. First-year (P1), second-year (P2), and third-year (P3) pharmacy students attended an education session during which types of plagiarism and methods for avoiding plagiarism were reviewed. Students completed a pre-intervention assessment immediately before the session and a post-intervention assessment the following semester to measure their ability. The results show that two hundred fifty-two students completed both pre-intervention and post-intervention assessments. There was a 4% increase from pre-intervention to post-intervention in assessment scores for the overall student sample ($p < 0.05$). The mean change was greatest for P1 and P2 students (5% and 4.8%, respectively). It was concluded that an educational intervention about plagiarism can significantly improve students' ability to identify plagiarism.

Evanson, Sponsel, and Davidson (2019) investigated how undergraduate students engage with digital news, researchers at Davidson College surveyed 511 incoming first-year students on their news consumption habits and asked them to evaluate screenshots of news stories. The researchers found that a high percentage of the students were accessing news through social media platforms and that syndication and fake URLs posed challenges for them in making accurate evaluations. Instrument for data collection was the mini-course management system moodle, and consisted of a survey and a set of exercises. The survey consisted of 9 to 14 branching questions, including multiple choice, Likert scale, open-ended response, and true-false survey questions. The survey and the exercise provided meaningful insights about how students engage with news in various digital formats. Student survey responses indicated they believe fake news is overall more a barrier for society than for themselves when asked how much of a barrier they perceive fake news to be to society's ability to recognize accurate information, the majority of students chose extreme or moderate on a Likert-scale, 41% ($n=210$) and 45% ($n=230$), respectively. However, when asked how much it is a barrier to their own ability to recognize accurate information, the majority chose moderate or somewhat, 27% ($n=136$) and 51% ($n=262$), respectively. Findings from the study shows that 24% ($n=125$) of students indicated that they could identify organized information from fake news on social media or other means.

Adile, and Bülent (2018) carried out a study to examine students' online information searching strategies, their cognitive absorption levels and the information pollution levels on the Internet based on different variables and to determine the correlation between these variables. The study was designed with the survey model, the study group included 198 students attending Computer Engineering and Computer Education and Instructional Technologies (CEIT) Departments in two universities located two cities in the Central Anatolian Region in 2016-2017 academic year fall semester. The data collection tools were Online

Information Searching Strategy Inventory, Internet Information Pollution Scale and Cognitive Absorption Scale. In the study, it was found that the scores of the students related to these variables were above the average. It was also found in the study that there were low levels of positive correlations between the students' level of cognitive absorption and encountering information pollution on the Internet and online information searching strategies. Another finding was that male students' average score for online information searching strategies was higher than that of the female students. Furthermore, the common interaction between department and grade level variables based on the Internet information pollution scores was statistically significant.

Aminu, and Adamu (2017) carried out a study that investigated the information search strategies on the use of electronic information resources by undergraduate students in the Federal Universities in Northern Nigeria. Quantitative research methodology was used for the study, and a total of two thousand four hundred and eighty-four (2,484) respondents were selected. A questionnaire was used to collect data from the respondents; the data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings revealed that the undergraduate students employed different search strategies while utilizing electronic information resources available in the universities. The search strategy used most is the Boolean operators and keyword searching, and the most used search engine is Google. The result of the study also revealed that there is a positive relationship between the information search strategies employed and the electronic information resources used. Based on the findings, the study recommends that the university management improve the content of the information literacy programmes in order to inculcate in the undergraduate students the knowledge of information search strategies. The study also recommends the library managements to assist the undergraduate students in the utilization of the available electronic information resources.

Adefunke and Oluwatosin (2023) conducted a study that assessed how digital literacy and online information searching strategies determine electronic resources' use among undergraduates of selected universities in Nigeria. The probability sampling technique was used in selecting the respondents for the study. The multi-stage sampling method was used to select 450 students from the three selected universities which formed the sample size of the study. Data was collected using the questionnaire on the digital literacy level of the students and the Tsai (2009) Online Information Searching Strategies Inventory (OISSI). A total of 450 copies of the questionnaire were administered, while 383 copies were filled, returned, and found valid for analysis. Findings showed that the undergraduates had a high level of digital literacy and their use of electronic resources was high. Online Information Searching Strategies Inventory and Digital Literacy jointly predicted the undergraduates' electronic resources' use significantly. Electronic resources are acquired in line with global best practices to impact the academic performance of undergraduates in higher educational institutions. However, literature has shown that electronic resources are not optimally used by undergraduates in Nigeria. This study, therefore, recommends continuous digital literacy skills training for undergraduates in Nigerian universities which would make them gain knowledge of the requisite skills necessary for the optimal use of electronic resources.

While students having naive epistemological beliefs and an inability to learn had lower-levels online searching strategies. Students having more web search experience had better online searching strategies. Additionally, as the level of students' mastery-approach goals increases, the use of procedural and meta-cognitive domain strategies increases as well, while the increase in the level of mastery-avoidance goals was related to the use of fewer behavioural domain strategies. Finally, students having rational decision styles were more likely to use higher levels of online information-searching strategies, while students with avoidant

styles tended to use less behavioural and procedural domain strategies.

Hogan, Varnhagen, and Varnhagen (2012) assessed the ability of 426 students (ages 12–13) to critically evaluate two types of online locations on health issues: an academic resource and a commercial resource. The results indicated limited evaluation abilities, especially for the commercial resource, and only a small, partial association with prior stance and offline reading ability. Only about half (51.4%) of the students questioned the credibility of the commercial online resource and only about 19% of the students showed an ability to fully recognize commercial bias. Wide variation existed in students' ability to evaluate online information, as approximately one-fourth of the students performed poorly when evaluating the overall credibility of both online resources, and one-fourth performed well. Logistic regression models showed that offline reading skills accounted for only 8.8% of the variance for the academic online resource and 15.1% of that for the commercial resource. No association appeared between evaluation and background knowledge, although an association with prior stance was observed for each online resource. The results are discussed in light of previous research and the need to pay greater attention to the critical evaluation of online resources during classroom instruction.

Lawal-Adebawale (2014) assessed the agro-students' appraisal of the online tool for course registration. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 325 agro-students, and a validated and reliable questionnaire was used for the collection of data on the study objectives. Results of the analysis data showed that the use of online registration tools was appraised as valuable for convenient course registration. The Spearman's rho correlation analysis of the study hypothesis showed a significant and positive association between the agro-students' appraisal of online registration of academic courses and their academic performance ($r = 0.155, p < 0.05$); educational background ($r = 0.128, p < 0.05$); mode of entry into FUNAAB ($r = 0.127, p < 0.05$). The linear regression analysis

showed that the students' appraisal of the online tool for registration of courses was significantly determined by their frequency of usage of the edu-portal ($\beta = 2.185, p < 0.01$). It was thus concluded that online registration of academic courses in FUNAAB is a worthwhile development and recommended that it should be sustained, and the students should be well trained on the usage of the edu-portal to develop skillful and efficient use of the online tool for registration of their academic courses.

Samiksha and Das (2019) examined evaluation of the use of college library resources and services by undergraduate students in the Darjeeling district of west Bengal. The study was conducted in 20 college libraries in the Darjeeling district of West Bengal to analyze the use of library resources and services by student users. The survey research method using structured questionnaires was adopted for the collection of data from the users. A total of 400 questionnaires were distributed randomly to the users, out of which 364 completely filled-in questionnaires were received back and included in the analysis. The findings reveal that the majority of student users visit the college libraries regularly mainly to borrow and return library books. Most of the college libraries have easily accessible locations, good layouts, sufficient lighting & ventilation, and neat & clean premises.

The college libraries mostly have a collection of text books but the collection of journals/magazines is found to be inadequate in many college libraries. It has been found that only a few college libraries offer open access to all documents, electronic information resources, daily newspapers, and syllabus & question papers to users. Most of the college libraries under study need to improve the services regarding the issuance of a sufficient number of documents, adequate numbers of computers for users, provision of internet and photocopy services, exhibition of newly acquired documents, reference service and reading tables, chairs & space. The lack of internet in the library, short library hours, lack of user orientation/education, and insufficient number of computers are found to

be the major problems identified to affect the use of the library.

Literature reviewed on the ability to identify, find, and evaluate information and effectively utilizes online library resources showed that these set of abilities are crucial skills for undergraduate students in their academic journey. These skills set, often referred to as information literacy, and involves a range of competencies that empower students to locate, evaluate, and use information effectively. Again, the ability of undergraduate students to identify information and effectively utilize online library resources is a multifaceted skills set that involves a combination of technical, critical thinking, and academic integrity competencies. Educational institutions, libraries, and faculty play a crucial role in fostering and assessing these skills throughout students' academic journeys.

Research Methodology

The Survey research design was used because, it was considered best in describing features of very large groups, and identifying the current conditions and needs, facts and opinion of library users regarding their information literacy skills. The research area was in the South-South zone of Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 12100 registered undergraduate library users from the University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun (997), Federal University, Otuoke, (1,363), University of Port-Harcourt (1,797), University of Uyo (1903), Delta State University Abraka (1,394), Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni (1,246), Niger Delta University Yenagoa (1593), Edo University Iyamo (1,203), Bayelsa Medical University (604). Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used in the selection of 605, a 5% of the registered library users for the study, (50 users from Federal University of Petroleum Resources, Effurun), (

University, Otuoke 68 users), (University of Port-Harcourt 90 users) (University of Uyo 95), (Delta State University Abraka 70), (Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni 62), (Niger Delta University Yenagoa 80), (Edo University Iyamo 60), (Bayelsa Medical University 30)

The instrument used was a 24 item likert type scale of Information Literacy skills and Utilization of Online Resources Questionnaire (ILUORQ). It had three parts, each with 8 items on each of the literacy abilities. To determine the reliability of the research instrument (questionnaire) a trial test was carried out using fifty (50) undergraduates from two university libraries, the University of Calabar and the University of Cross River State, that were not part of the selected institutions under investigation. The Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to determine the reliability estimate of the instrument. The questionnaire was administered by trained research assistants from each university libraries, five hundred and ninety-three (593) out of (605) respondents sampled was used for the study.

Data Analysis and Results

Data for each hypothesis is re-stated, and the result of the data analysis carried out to test it is presented. Each hypothesis of the study was tested at a .05 level of significance.

1. Hypothesis one

The ability to identify information does not significantly predict the utilization of online resources

The independent variable in this hypothesis is the ability to identify information; while the dependent variable is the utilization of online resources. Simple regression analysis was the statistical tool employed to test this hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Simple regression result of the relationship between ability to identify information and utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study

Model	R	R. square	Adjusted R. square	Std error of the estimate		
1	.816(a)	.665	.665	1.59457		
Model	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F		p-value
Regression	2992.190	1	2992.190	176.793		.000(a)
Residual	1505.258	592	2.543			
Total	4497.448	593				
Variables	Unstandardized regression weight B	Standardized regression weight	Beta weight	t		p-value
(Constant)	9.596	.688		13.950		.000
Ability to identify information	.800	.023	.816	34.304		.000

* Significant at .05 level.

The simple regression analysis of the prediction of the Ability to identify information on the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study produced an adjusted R² of .665. This indicates that the ability to identify information accounts for 66.5% of the variance in the utilization of online resources of the undergraduates sampled for the study. This finding is a critical indication that the ability to identify information is relatively high in the area of the study.

The F-value of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was $F = 176.793$ and the sig. value of .000 (or $p < .05$) at the degree of freedom (df) 1 and 592. This result implies that the ability to identify information is a significant predictor of the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study sample for the study. The identified equation to understand this relationship was that Utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study = $9.60 + 0.80$ (Ability to identify information).

2. Hypothesis two

The capacity to find information does not significantly predict the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study in university libraries in south-south Nigeria

The independent variable in this hypothesis is the Capacity to find information; while the dependent variable is the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study. Simple regression analysis was employed to test this hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 2

TABLE 2

Simple regression result of the prediction of Capacity to find information on utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study.

Model	R	R. square	Adjusted R. square	Std error of the estimate		
1	.729(a)	.531	.530	1.88719		
Model	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F		p-value
Regression	2389.051	1	2389.051	670.802*		.000(a)
Residual	2108.397	592	3.561			
Total	4497.448	593				
Variables	Unstandardized regression weight B	Standardized regression weight	Beta weight	t		p-value
(Constant)	13.916	.744		18.698		.000
Ability to find information	.655	.025	.729	25.900		.000

* Significant at .05 level.

The simple regression analysis of the prediction of Capacity to find information on the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study produced an adjusted R² of .530. This indicated that the Capacity to find information accounted for 53.0% of the variance in the utilization of online resources of the undergraduates sampled for the study area. This finding is a critical indication that the Capacity to find information is relatively high in the area of the study. The F-value of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) obtained from the regression table was $F = 670.802$ and the sig. value of .000 (or $p < .05$) at the degree of freedom (df) 1 and 592. This result implies that the Capacity to find information is a significant predictor of the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study sample for the study.

The identified equation to understand this relationship was that Utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study = $13.92 + 0.66$ (Capacity to find information).

3. Hypothesis three

Skills to evaluate information do not significantly predict the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study in university libraries in south-south Nigeria.

The independent variable in this hypothesis is the skills to evaluate information; while the dependent variable is the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study. Simple regression analysis was employed to test this hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Simple regression result of the relationship between skills to evaluate information and utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study

Model	R	R. square	Adjusted R. square	Std error of the estimate		
1	.774(a)	.600	.599	1.74368		
Model	Sum of square	Df	Mean square	F		p-value
Regression	2697.517	1	2697.517	887.217*		.000(a)
Residual	1799.931	592	3.040			
Total	4497.448	593				
Variables	Unstandardized regression weight B	Standardized regression weight	Beta weight	t		p-value
(Constant)	11.818	.718		16.469		.000
Ability to evaluate information	.726	.024	.774	29.786		.000

* Significant at .05 level.

The simple regression analysis of the prediction of skills to evaluate information on the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study produced an adjusted R² of .599. This indicated that the skills to evaluate information accounted for 59.9% of the variance in the utilization of online resources of the undergraduates sampled for the study area. This finding is a critical indication that skills to evaluate information is relatively high in the area of the study. The F-value of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) obtained from the regression table was $F = 887.217$ and the sig. value of .000 (or $p < .05$) at the degree of freedom (df) 1 and 592. This result implies that the skills to evaluate information is a significant predictor of the utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study.

The identified equation to understand this relationship was that Utilization of online resources by undergraduates sampled for the study = $11.818 + .726$ (Skills to evaluate information).

Discussion of the Findings

The result of the first hypothesis indicates that the ability to identify information significantly predicts the utilization of online resources by the undergraduates sampled for the study. The finding

is in line with the view of Ikenwe & Anaehobi (2020), who investigated the relationship between lecturers' ability to identify the extent of information need, access information, and utilization of digital library resources in Federal Universities, in Southern Nigeria. Their findings revealed that there is a positive relationship between abilities to identify the extent of information, and access information in the utilization of digital library resources. Their findings provided novel facts that help to clarify existing uncertainties and ambiguity in the link between some elements of information literacy and the use of digital library resources in developing economies such as Nigeria.

Moreover, the finding aligns with previous studies that have highlighted the importance of information literacy in the academic environment. For instance, Ani and Ahiauzu (2018) reported that students with higher levels of information literacy are better equipped to utilize online resources, which in turn positively impacts their academic performance. This correlation suggests that information literacy should be a key component of university curricula, especially in a digitally-driven educational landscape where online resources are abundant yet complex to navigate. The ability to identify relevant information amidst a vast array of digital content

is crucial for undergraduates to leverage the full benefits of online academic resources.

The significant predictive power of information identification skills on the utilization of online resources also has implications for library services in Nigerian universities. Libraries must prioritize the development of information literacy programs that target the enhancement of students' skills in identifying and accessing online information. According to Okiy (2019), university libraries should adopt proactive strategies, such as workshops and online tutorials, to teach students how to effectively search for, evaluate, and use digital resources. These initiatives would not only improve students' academic outcomes but also contribute to the overall goal of producing information-literate graduates.

The result of the second hypothesis demonstrates that the capacity to find information significantly predicts the utilization of online resources by undergraduates in university libraries in Nigeria. This finding emphasizes the importance of students' search skills in their ability to access and make use of the vast array of digital academic resources available. According to Ukwoma et al. (2017), the ability to efficiently locate relevant information within online databases, academic journals, and other digital platforms is a critical determinant of how effectively students can utilize these resources for academic purposes. This capacity is crucial in a digital environment where information is abundant but often difficult to sift through without proper search skills.

Furthermore, this finding aligns with the broader body of research that links search skills with academic success. Studies by Issa et al. (2018) have shown that students who are proficient in navigating online resources tend to have higher academic performance, as they are able to find and use information more effectively than their peers with lower search skills. This suggests that the ability to locate information is not only a predictor of resource utilization but also a key factor in overall academic achievement. Therefore, enhancing students' search skills should be a priority for university libraries and educators.

The result of the third hypothesis indicates that the skills to evaluate information significantly predict the utilization of online resources by undergraduates in university libraries in Nigeria. This finding highlights the importance of critical evaluation skills in effectively using digital academic resources. In an era where information is easily accessible but often overwhelming in volume and variable in quality, the ability to assess the credibility, relevance, and accuracy of information is crucial. According to Igwe and Onyekweodiri (2018), students who possess strong information evaluation skills are more adept at discerning which resources are academically sound and which are not, leading to more effective and efficient use of online resources.

Moreover, the significant relationship between evaluation skills and online resource utilization aligns with previous research that underscores the role of critical thinking in academic success. As Okiki and Asiru (2019) observed, students with well-developed evaluation skills are more likely to engage deeply with the materials they find, critically analyzing and synthesizing information rather than passively consuming it. This active engagement not only enhances the quality of their academic work but also increases their overall academic performance. Therefore, fostering these skills is essential for ensuring that students can navigate the complexities of digital information environments effectively.

The predictive power of information evaluation skills on resource utilization also has important implications for the design of information literacy programs in Nigerian university libraries. As observed by Abubakar and Hasan (2020), many students struggle with the evaluation of online information due to a lack of formal training in critical thinking and information literacy. University libraries should, therefore, incorporate more robust training modules focused on teaching students how to critically assess digital content. This could include workshops, online tutorials, and interactive sessions that guide students through the process of evaluating sources for authority, bias, and reliability.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study it was concluded that the ability to identify information, capacity to find information, aptitude to evaluate information, significantly predict utilization of online resources by undergraduates in university libraries in South-South Nigeria

The findings of the study emphasize the importance of undergraduates' ability to identify relevant information as a key predictor of their effective use of online resources in university libraries. This suggests that students who are more adept at discerning what information they need are better positioned to utilize online academic resources effectively. Consequently, fostering this ability through targeted training programs could significantly enhance the academic experience for students, enabling them to make more informed use of available digital resources.

In addition to the ability to identify information, the capacity to find the necessary information was also found to be a significant predictor of online resource utilization. This finding underscores the importance of search and retrieval skills in the academic environment. Students who possess the knowledge and ability to navigate complex online databases and information repositories are more likely to use online resources productively. Therefore, equipping students with efficient search techniques and knowledge of various online platforms should be a priority for academic institutions.

The study revealed that the skills to evaluate information critically play a crucial role in the effective utilization of online resources. This suggests that undergraduates who can assess the credibility, relevance, and quality of the information they encounter are more likely to engage with online resources in a meaningful way. Developing critical evaluation skills among students is therefore essential, as it ensures they can make informed decisions about which resources to rely on for their academic work, ultimately leading to improved learning outcomes.

Recommendations

- 1) **Enhance Information Identification Skills:** University libraries should implement training programs and workshops that focus on improving students' ability to identify relevant information. This can be done through structured information literacy courses integrated into the academic curriculum, where students learn how to determine what information is necessary for their academic tasks, thus enabling more efficient utilization of online resources.
- 2) **Develop Effective Information Retrieval Techniques:** Academic institutions should prioritize teaching students how to find information within online databases and digital platforms. Offering tutorials on advanced search strategies, database navigation, and the use of library resources will equip students with the tools they need to access and retrieve information more effectively, thus enhancing their ability to utilize online resources.
- 3) **Strengthen Critical Evaluation Skills:** Universities should provide training to help students critically evaluate the information they access online. This could include lessons on assessing the credibility, relevance, and accuracy of sources, ensuring that students are equipped to make informed decisions about which online resources to rely on for academic purposes. This would not only improve the quality of their academic work but also foster responsible and ethical use of information.

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